

8 December 1971

Dear Mr Williamson

Thank you for your letter of 27 November. It is very nice to know that you think this project is worth pushing along.

However before answering your queries I feel I ought to explain the situation on salaries as it now stands. As you will have seen from my letter to Miss de Cardi of 20 September, we were hoping to get someone on more or less the same terms that are applied to VSO type volunteers (of which there are three here now and a fourth expected). This amounts to about £40 a month, air fares, accommodation and local transport. The £40 was worked out (by me) as being a reasonable living wage - VSOs are only supposed to earn enough to keep themselves. What happened then was that our hopes here were raised that the Ruler might authorise funds to pay a proper professional salary which would make the job obviously much more attractive. Having received several letters of enquiry from very well qualified people, this possibility has alas been ruled out, for the time being anyway. So we are back to square one and can only offer the terms originally stated, which the Municipality can meet from its existing budget without requiring an extra grant from the Ruler.

From your letter I'm not quite sure whether you were thinking of the post as a professionally paid one (in which case I'm afraid you will no longer be interested) or a being on what amounts to a board-and-lodging basis (in which case I hope are still interested). Perhaps you could let me know. If you are willing to come on these terms I will certainly take up the question of a double air fare with the Municipality and also try to answer the questions you raised in your letter.

Yours sincerely

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